

Identification of legumains
encoded by the genome of *Theobroma cacao* and analysis of expression pattern

Santana, JO¹; Santos, LF¹; Sousa, AO¹; Soares, VLF¹; Pirovani, CP¹

¹Universidade Estadual de Santa Cruz, Centro de Biotecnologia e Genética, Rodovia Ilhéus-Itabuna, Km 16, 45662-000, Ilhéus-BA, Brasil

Keywords: gene expression, *Theobroma cacao*, legumain.

The legumains are cysteine proteases belonging to the C13 family (EC 3.4.22.34) found in various types of plants. These proteins are called vacuolar processing enzyme (VPE) or asparaginyl endopeptidase (AEP), by recognize and cleave after asparagine residues (Asn) or aspartate (Asp) into polypeptides. These enzymes are classified according to the tissues which are most expressed. The vegetative VPE are mainly involved in the processes of senescence, response to stress, plant development and response to pathogens. The VPEs seeds are involved in processing and mobilization of storage proteins and seed development. Exist yet is another group of legumains localized in the cell wall of the cells. In order to characterize the legumains *Theobroma cacao*, *in silico* analyzes were performed on genomic data bank – CocoaGen and the expression pattern of the identified genes was analyzed by RT-qPCR in different tissues - leaf, stem, root, tegument and seeds during germination and during development. Total RNA was extracted, treated with DNase I and used for cDNA synthesis. Expression levels were analyzed in biological replicates and experimental quintuplicate. The expression data were analyzed by Method $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ using the average of gene expression. Of actin, malate dehydrogenase and glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase as an endogenous normalizer. As result of the alignment between cocoa legumains with other species already identified, three genes were found at loci Tc03_g025550 (1470pb, 489aa e 54.4kDa), Tc06_g006030 (1452pb, 483aa e 53.9 kDa) and Tc09_g004580 (1464pb, 487aa e 53.8 kDa). These were named TcLeg3, TcLeg6 e TcLeg9. The alignment between the three VPEs with a sequence of *Arabidopsis thaliana* legumain demonstrated similarity 73.0% (TcLeg3), 57.2% (TcLeg6) e 74.1% (TcLeg9). The cysteine and histidine residues that are part of the catalytic site between proteins were conserved. The relative expression analysis, and the seed as calibrator, demonstrated low accumulation of transcripts *TcLeg3* for all tissues analyzed, being less expressed in the root (0.04-*X*). Contrary, the *TcLeg9* showed increased expression in all tissues, being sheet the highest expression (18.9-*X*). On the other hand, the TcLeg6 was only detected in developing seeds. In germinating seeds, the transcripts TcLeg3 was decreasing of initial time until the thirtieth day (1.00 para 0.011-*X*). Still in the same tissue, the expression of *TcLeg9* was growing until the twentieth day (1.00 para 48.96-*X*). The obtained expression profile suggests that the TcLeg3 associated to germination of seed, while TcLeg9 is related to the development of the plant. The TcLeg6 may be involved with the removal of the inner layers necessary for the formation of tegument.

Financial Support: FAPESB